

The Rotatory Powers of Substituted Camphoranilic Acids.

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The present work is in continuation of the work already reported in a series of communications (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1966; 1927, 1944; 1928, 2410; 1930, 1301; 1931, 478; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 363, 1934, 11, 433). The following acids have now been prepared: 2'-and 4'-ethyl-, 3'-and 4'-fluoro-, 3'-and 4'-nitro-, 3'-and 4'-amino-, 3'-and 4'-acetylamino-, 3'-and 4'-acetyl-, 2'-nitro-4'ethyl-, 2'-nitro-3'-fluoro-, 2'-nitro-4'-fluoro-, 2'-nitro-4'-acetylcamphoranilic acids.

In the case of fluoro-, nitro-, amino-, acetylamino- and acetocamphoranilic acids, the *para* isomeride has a greater rotatory power than the corresponding *meta* derivative. The rotatory powers of ethylcamphoranilic acids (Table I) are of the same order as those of the methylcamphoranilic acids.

TABLE I.

Solvent.	<i>o</i> -Me.	<i>p</i> -Me.	<i>o</i> -Et.	<i>p</i> -Et.
MeOH	151°	170°	153°	170°
EtOH	127	137	137	145
Me ₂ CO	98	122	117	102
MeEtCO	90	—	94	112

Table II gives the rotatory powers of *m*- and *p*-methyl and *m*- and *p*-acetocamphoranilic acids.

TABLE II.

Solvent.	<i>m</i> -Me.	<i>m</i> -COMe.	<i>p</i> -Me.	<i>p</i> -COMe.
MeOH	137°	118°	170°	214°
EtOH	121	99	137	215
Me ₂ CO	95	61	122	164
MeEtCO	108	71	—	161

The introduction of the carbonyl group caused an increase in the rotatory power of methylcamphoranilic acid. Rule and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 553) have also shown that the acetyl group, like other positive groups, produces an exaltation in the rotatory power. In the *meta* position, however, there is a fall in all the four solvents.

Table III records the rotatory powers of *meta*- and *para*- fluoro-, chloro-, bromo-, iodocamphoranilic acids in methyl alcohol and acetone.

TABLE III.

Solvent.	<i>m</i> -F.	<i>m</i> -Cl.	<i>m</i> -Br.	<i>m</i> -I.
MeOH	154°	162°	157°	167°
Me ₂ CO	104	97	111	119
	<i>p</i> -F.	<i>p</i> -Cl.	<i>p</i> -Br.	<i>p</i> -I.
MeOH	125	183	182	177
Me ₂ CO	54	119	125	146

The rotatory powers of *m*-fluoro acid are of the same order as those of the other *meta*- halogeno acids but in the *para*-fluoro acid there is a remarkable decrease particularly in acetone. It has not been possible to prepare *o*-fluorocamphoranilic acid and, therefore, the effect of the fluorine atom in the *ortho*-position has not been studied. It is, however, expected that it would give an abnormally low value.

The nitro group in the *meta*-position has a depressing effect. The rotatory power of *m*-nitrocamphoranilic acid is the lowest as shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

<i>m</i> -COOH.	<i>m</i> -Br.	<i>m</i> -OEt.	<i>m</i> -I.	<i>m</i> -OMe.	<i>m</i> -Cl.	<i>m</i> -F.	<i>m</i> -Me.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .
466°	182°	179°	177°	163°	162°	153°	140°	138°

The nitro group in the *para*-position produces a small increase in the rotatory power of camphoranilic acid. It has been mentioned before that this group in the *para*-position in disubstituted camphoranilic acids has a depressing effect. The nitro group is strongly polar and it was expected that *p*-nitrocamphoranilic acid would give values of the order of *p*-carboxycamphoranilic acid. This behaviour of the nitro group is,

therefore, abnormal. The *m*- and *p*-nitrocamphoranilic acids have been reduced by ferrous sulphate and ammonia, the procedure given in literature being modified in minor details. The yield of the aminocamphoranilic acid is satisfactory but the purification is rather tedious. The amino groups are shown to have produced an exaltation of rotation but not to the extent as was expected. This may be due to the presence of a carboxylic group in the molecule.

The acetylaminocamphoranilic acids were prepared by acetylating the above amino acids and also by condensing camphoric anhydride with *m*- and *p*-aminoacetanilides. They were shown to be identical by mixed melting point.

The rotatory powers of the free amino acids and the acetylated products are shown in Table V.

TABLE V.

Solvent.	<i>m</i> -NH ₂ .	<i>m</i> -NHCOMe.	<i>p</i> -NH ₂	<i>p</i> -NHCOMe.
MeOH	134°	83·0°	166·8°	169·6°
EtOH	120	76·3	154·0	161·4
Me ₂ CO	124	56·0	—	141·0
MeEtCO	124·4	67·0	—	142·0

The *m*-acetylaminocamphoranilic acid has lower values than the *m*-amino acid in all the four solvents. The *p*-amino acid could only be examined in alcohols, because in the other two solvents it gave coloured solutions which could not be viewed clearly. In these solvents the values are slightly lower than the corresponding values of *p*-acetylaminocamphoranilic acid.

The following acids have been nitrated: 3'-fluoro-, 4'-fluoro-, 4'-ethyl-, 4'-acetocamphoranilic acids. The nitration of 4'-chloro-, 4'-bromo-, 4'-methylcamphoranilic acids has been described by Singh and Singh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 478). The rotatory powers of these nitro acids are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Acids.	MeOH.	EtOH.	Me ₂ CO.	MeEtCO.
4'-Fluoro-2'-nitro-	-45·0°	-49·6°	-47·6°	-47·5
4'-Chloro-2'-nitro-	-40·8	-51·8	-47·2	-35·2
4'-Bromo-2'-nitro-	-39·2	-45·3	-35·9	-31·5
4'-Methyl-2'-nitro-	-50·0	-60·5	-48·1	-41·2
4'-Ethyl-2'-nitro-	-62·1	-72·9	-67·3	-60·6

In every case the nitro group in the 2'-position depresses the rotatory power of the original compound and produces reversal in the sign of rotation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Camphoric Anhydride with Mono-substituted Amines.

Camphoric anhydride and different amines in equimolecular proportions were heated with a little fused sodium acetate for 3-4 hours in an oil-bath at 120-150° and the product extracted with a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide or ammonium hydroxide to remove any imide which might have been formed during the condensation. The filtrate was acidified with dilute acetic acid and the solid mass thus formed crystallised from dilute alcohol (animal charcoal).

o-Ethylcamphoranilic Acid crystallised from dilute alcohol as a white powder, darkening at 165° and melting at 171°. It is soluble in the usual organic solvents, but insoluble in water. (Found: N, 4.70; Equiv., 301. $C_{18}H_{23}O_3N$ requires N, 4.62 per cent. Equiv., 303).

p-Ethylcamphoranilic Acid crystallised from dilute alcohol as a white microcrystalline mass, softening at 200° and melting at 202-203°. It is soluble in the usual organic solvents but insoluble in water. (Found: N, 4.72; Equiv., 301.5. $C_{18}H_{23}O_3N$ requires N, 4.62 per cent. Equiv., 303).

m-Acetylcamphoranilic Acid is a light brown fluffy mass, m.p. 189-90°. (Found: N, 4.54; Equiv., 315. $C_{18}H_{23}O_4N$ requires N, 4.41 per cent. Equiv., 317).

p-Acetylcamphoranilic Acid crystallised from dilute alcohol as a white crystalline mass with a very slight yellow tinge, m.p. 224-25°. (Found: N, 4.53; Equiv., 316. $C_{18}H_{23}O_4N$ requires N, 4.41 per cent. Equiv., 317).

m-Nitrocamphoranilic Acid.—Condensation temperature 140-150° for 4 hours, or 180° for 5-10 minutes. It is a light yellow crystalline mass, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 8.89. $C_{16}H_{20}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.75 per cent).

p-Nitrocamphoranilic Acid.—Condensation temperature 140-150° for 4 hours, but the yield was better at 180° for 5-10 minutes. It is a light yellow microcrystalline mass, m.p. 202-203°. It is soluble in

the usual organic solvents, insoluble in water. (Found : N, 8.87-
 $C_{16}H_{20}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.75 per cent).

Reduction of Nitrocamphoranilic Acids.

To a boiling solution of 36 g. of ferrous sulphate dissolved in a small quantity of water an ammoniacal solution of the acid (3 g.) was added in small quantities with continuous shaking. When the whole of the acid solution had been added, liquor ammonia was added until the colour of the reaction mixture became black. It was then concentrated and filtered and the filtrate acidified with acetic acid and the precipitate obtained on cooling was crystallised from dilute alcohol.

m-Aminocamphoranilic Acid crystallised from dilute alcohol as a white mass having a slight pinkish tinge, m.p. 196-97°. (Found : N, 9.85. Equiv., 291. $C_{16}H_{22}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.65 per cent. Equiv., 290).

p-Aminocamphoranilic Acid could not be recrystallised from dilute alcohol as it decomposed on crystallisation. It was purified by repeated precipitation and dissolution. It was obtained as a fine pinkish powder, m.p. 220-21°. (Found : N, 9.76; Equiv., 289. $C_{16}H_{22}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.65 per cent. Equiv., 290).

m-Acetylaminoamphoranilic Acid.—Temperature of condensation 140-150° for 4 hours. It is a white shining crystalline powder, m.p. 220-21°. (Found : N, 8.57; Equiv., 330. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.43 per cent. Equiv., 332).

p-Acetylaminoamphoranilic Acid.—Condensation temperature 170-180° for 4 hours. It crystallised from dilute alcohol as a white mass with a slight pinkish tinge darkening at 231-32° and melting at 234-35°. (Found : N, 8.52; Equiv., 330. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.43 per cent., Equiv., 332).

m-Fluorocamphoranilic Acid.—Condensation temperature 130-140° for 3 hours. It crystallised as white mica-like shining crystals, m.p. 197°. (Found : N, 4.85. Equiv., 290. $C_{16}H_{20}O_3NF$ requires N, 4.77 per cent. Equiv., 293).

p-Fluorocamphoranilic Acid.—Condensation temperature 180° for 5 minutes or 140° for 4 hours, but in the latter case some imide was formed. The substance could not be crystallised from any solvent, hence it was purified by repeated precipitation and dissolution, m.p. 180-81°. (Found : N, 4.86; Equiv., 291. $C_{16}H_{20}O_3NF$ requires N, 4.77 per cent. Equiv., 293).

Nitration.

The acid (3 g.) was added in small quantities at a time to a mixture of 10 c.c. of fuming nitric acid and 8 c.c. of glacial acetic acid cooled in ice and thoroughly shaken. The solution was cooled in ice for 45 minutes after which it was poured into ice. The precipitate was crystallised from dilute alcohol, yield theoretical.

2'-Nitro-4'-ethylcamphoranilic Acid crystallised from dilute alcohol in a fine yellow crystalline fluffy mass, m.p. 140-5°. (Found : N, 8.20. $C_{18}H_{24}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.05 per cent).

2'-Nitro-3'-fluorocamphoranilic Acid separated from dilute alcohol as a yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 131-32°. (Found : N, 8.41. $C_{16}H_{19}O_5N_2F$ requires N, 8.28 per cent).

2'-Nitro-4'-fluorocamphoranilic Acid separated from dilute alcohol as a fine dark yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 171°. It is soluble in organic solvents and insoluble in water. (Found : N, 8.44. $C_{16}H_{19}O_5N_2F$ requires N, 8.28 per cent).

2'-Nitro-4'-acetocamphoranilic Acid crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow plates, m.p. 202-203°. (Found : N, 7.82. $C_{18}H_{24}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.73 per cent).

o-Ethylcamphorophenylimide.—Temperature of condensation 180-200° for 4 hours. It crystallised from dilute alcohol as a white mass with a slight pinkish tinge, m.p. 132-33°. (Found : N, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{23}O_2N$ requires N, 4.91 per cent).

p-Ethylcamphorophenylimide.—Temperature of condensation was 200°. Slight traces of the acid were washed out with dilute ammonia. The insoluble imide was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white shining crystals, m.p. 123°. It is soluble in the usual organic solvents, insoluble in water. (Found : N, 4.97. $C_{18}H_{23}O_2N$ requires N, 4.91 per cent).

The rotations were determined by dissolving a known weight of the substance in a known volume of the solvent. The following results, without any mutarotation, were obtained. The length of the polarimeter tube was 2 dcm. in all cases. The temperature of the dark room varied between 17°-19°.

TABLE VII.

Solvent*	Conc.	[α].	[α] _D .	Conc.	[α].	[α] _D .
	<i>o</i> -Ethyl-				<i>p</i> -Ethyl-	
A	0.2000 g./25 c.c.	0.81	50.6	0.2027 g./25 c.c.	0.96	59.2

TABLE VII. (contd.)

Solvent.	Conc.	$[\alpha]$.	$[\alpha]_D$.	Conc.	$[\alpha]$.	$[\alpha]_D$.
	<i>o</i> -Ethyl-			<i>p</i> -Ethyl-		
B	0.2179 g./25 c.c.	0.79	45.3	0.2035 g./25 c.c.	0.78	47.9
C	0.2002	0.50	31.2	0.2027	0.60	37.0
D	0.2032	0.63	38.8	0.2070	0.56	33.8
	<i>m</i> -Aceto-			<i>p</i> -Aceto-		
A	0.2000	0.59	36.9	0.2018	1.09	67.5
B	0.2025	0.50	30.9	0.2013	1.09	67.7
C	0.2001	0.31	19.4	0.2004	0.83	51.8
D	0.2034	0.33	20.3	0.2041	0.83	50.8
	<i>m</i> -Nitro-			<i>p</i> -Nitro-		
A	0.2055	0.71	43.2	0.2000	1.21	75.6
B	0.2025	0.55	34.0	0.2088	1.19	71.2
C	0.2008	0.41	25.5	0.2029	0.92	56.6
D	0.2020	0.45	27.8	0.2002	1.03	64.3
	<i>m</i> -Amino-			<i>p</i> -Amino-		
A	0.2000	0.71	46.3	0.1000	0.46	57.5
B	0.2008	0.67	41.7	0.2000	0.85	53.1
C	0.1924	0.66	42.8			
D	0.1969	0.66	42.9			
	<i>m</i> -Acetylamino-			<i>p</i> -Acetylamino-		
A	0.2000	0.40	25.0	0.2006	0.82	51.1
B	0.2012	0.37	23.0	0.1980	0.77	48.6
C	0.2069	0.28	16.9	0.2002	0.68	42.5
D	0.2042	0.33	20.2	0.2014	0.69	42.8

* A = Methyl alcohol; B = Acetone; C = Ethyl alcohol;
D = Methyleneethyl ketone.

TABLE VII. (contd.).

Solvent.	Conc.	[α].	[α] _D .	Conc.	[α].	[α] _D .
	<i>m</i> -Fluoro-			<i>p</i> -Fluoro-		
A	0.2005	0.84	52.4	0.2047	0.70	42.7
B	0.2038	0.66	40.5	0.2044	0.67	41.0
C	0.2032	0.57	35.4	0.2024	0.50	18.5
D	0.2007	0.54	33.6	0.2100	0.44	26.2
	<i>2'</i> -Nitro-4'-ethyl-			<i>2'</i> -Nitro-3'-fluoro-		
A	0.2012 g./25 c.c.	-1.00	-62.1	0.2000 g./25 c.c.	-0.23	-14.4
B	0.2023	-1.18	-72.9	0.2000	-0.40	-25.0
C	0.2005	-1.08	-67.3	0.2000	-0.31	-19.4
D	0.2002	-0.97	-50.6	0.2000	-0.17	-10.6
	<i>2'</i> -Nitro-4'-fluoro-			<i>2'</i> -Nitro-4'-aceto-		
A	0.2000	-0.72	-45.0	0.2003	0.83	51.8
B	0.2066	-0.82	-49.6	0.2000	0.71	44.4
C	0.2100	-0.80	-47.6	0.2001	0.67	41.8
D	0.2000	-0.76	-47.5	0.2002	0.63	39.3
	<i>o</i> -Ethylcamphorophenylimide			<i>p</i> -Ethylcamphorophenylimide		
A	0.4008	0.63	19.6	0.4005	0.51	15.9
B	0.3945	0.62	19.7	0.4910	0.57	14.5
C	0.3996	0.51	16.0	0.4000	0.51	15.9
D	0.3952	0.50	15.8	0.4002	0.43	13.4

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